
EVALUATION OF THE EFFICACY OF SOME PLANT LEAF EXTRACTS ON INSECT PEST INFESTATION, GROWTH AND YIELD OF CUCUMBER IN OKIGWE SOUTH-EASTERN NIGERIA.

**Ibekwe, H.N, Nwanguma E.I, Uwalaka O.A , Opara, S.C, Ngbede, S.O and Onyegbule .U.
National Horticultural Research Institute, P.M.B 1076, Okigwe, Imo State. Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

Field experiments were carried out at the National Horticultural Research Institute, Okigwe, Imo State during the late cropping of 2012 and was repeated at the same cropping season in 2013 to evaluate the efficacies of some ethanol plant leaf extracts namely: garlic (*Allium sativum*), Neem (*Azadiracta indica*), *Ocimum gratissimum*, *Moringa olifera* and tithonia on the insect pests of cucumber. The treatments consisted of three levels of concentration of each of the five extracts namely 50%, 75% and 100% as well as distilled water, concentrated water and synthetic insecticide cypermethrine at 12.5% E.C. There were eighteen treatments for each season which were replicated three times in a split-plot experimental design. Results of the studies showed the identified commonest insect pest of the crop in the 2012 and 2013 cropping seasons to include flea beetles (*Cerotoma ruficornis*), cucumber beetle, *Leptoglossus autralis* and *Diabrotica* spp. The results also demonstrated that all the tested plant extracts at bi-weekly spraying interval were efficacious in controlling the insect pests. The efficacy of *Allium sativum* at 100% concentration was highest of all the plant extracts where 0.84kg/plot and 1.05kg/plot were recorded in 2012 and 2013 seasons respectively. This was followed by 100% concentration of *Azadirachta indica*, 100% *ocimum*, 100% *Moringa olifera* and tithonia in that order. The efficacy of the cypermethrine (synthetic insecticidal check) was highest having performed best. Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) existed between the untreated (control) and all the treated plots in insect population and yield. However, the tested plant extracts at the three different concentration of 50%, 75% and 100% in both seasons proved efficacious in the control of the insect pests of cucumber as 78.2% reduction in insect population, 79.8% reduction in leaf damage and 79.3% marketable fruit number were recorded in 2012 and 82.7% reduction in insect population, 76.4% reduction in leaf damage and 85.9% marketable fruit number in 2013 cropping season.

KEYWORDS: cucumber, extracts, efficacy, insect pest

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Corresponding Author: Hyginusibekwe@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) belongs to the family Cucurbitaceae. It is an annual monoecious herb with trailing stems up to 5m long. It has the origin from North America and now it is widespread throughout the world (Tindall, 1983). It is widely cultivated for the production of its edible fruits which can be consumed raw or cooked. Also it is cultivated for fresh fruit and pickling which are locally consumed or exported to increase National income. (Herbert, 1990). Oil is obtained from the seed which can be used in salad dressing and fresh cooking (Faciola 1990). The fruit

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is usually elongated and used externally as a poultice for burns and fresh fruit also used internally in the treatment of blemish skin and heat rash. The leaves are used as vegetables in Malaysia and have medicinal use in India for throat infection as a diuretic (Messiaen, 1992; Grieve 1984).

Cucumber production in Nigeria is rapidly increasing as the crop is cultivated in most parts of Northern Nigeria and some parts of the Eastern Nigeria by peasant farmers with the attendant high yield annually (Ekwu *et al*, 2007). However, insect pests and diseases tend to be a major constraint for the production of this crop. In Nigeria, heavy losses as high as 85% occur due to the infestation of the crop by the associated major insect pests (Boorman, 1981).

The management of insect pests on vegetables has been achieved successfully with the use of conventional insecticides but the problem associated with this such as environmental pollution, health risks etc. has led to the development of alternative strategies for sustainable pest management which are safe, cheap, non-toxic and simple to adopt (Dales, 1996). A number of tropical plant species have been observed to have medicinal properties, which suggest that natural insecticides may be derived from them (Onifade, 2000). Reports by various authors have shown that *A. indica*, *O. gratissimum*, *A.sativum* and *M. olifera* have considerable potentials for use in the control of insect pests (Ofuya *et al.*, 2005; NRC, 1992). To ensure as well as sustain steady availability of this crop and on a large scale, adequate and environmentally safe control measures are necessary and hence the need for this trial which aims at developing a cheap, environmentally safe, easy to apply, simple to adopt as well as sustainable pest management method using aqueous extracts of *Ocimum*, *Allium sativum*, *Azadirachata indica*, *Moringa olifera* and *Tithonia* for effective control of insect pests of cucumber in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

These experiments were conducted during the late season planting between August and November of 2012 and 2013 at the experimental site of National Horticultural Research Institute Mbato Okigwe Sub-station in Imo State. The area is situated in the humid rainforest zone of Nigeria and lies on latitude 05^o33N and longitude 07^o23E with an altitude of 130 meters above sea level. The mean temperature of the area varies between 27^oC and 28^oC with relative humidity and mean annual rainfall of 78% and 2048mm respectively.

SOIL ANALYSIS

A pre-planting soil sample was collected from a depth of 0-20cm using soil sampling auger. The soil sample was air dried, sieved using a 2mm mesh size sieve and then subjected to routine laboratory analyses. Organic matter (O.M) was determined by Walkley –Black dichromate digestion method (Nelson and Sommers,1982) and total soil nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl method (Bremaer and Muivancy,1982). Available P was determined by Bray-1 method (Murphy and Riley, 1962). Exchangeable K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ were extracted using ammonium acetate. Potassium was determined using Flame photometer and Ca and Mg by EDTA titrator. The soil PH in 0.01M CaCl₂ was determined using glass electrode.

The soil of the study area is classified as utisoll derived from shale/sandstone. The soil was sandy loam (743g/kg sand, 155g/kg silt, 122g/kg clay) characterised by low organic matter, low C.E.C and are highly leached (Onweremadu *et. al*, 2011). The physical and chemical properties of the soil are presented in Table 1.

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Table 1: Some physical and chemical composition of soil used for the trial.

Properties	Soil
pH	4.98
Total N (g/kg)	0.90
Available P (mg/kg)	6.80
Exch. K (cmol/kg)	0.19
Exch. Ca (cmol/kg)	3.20
Exch. Mg (cmol/kg)	1.60
Organic matter (g/kg)	0.17

Land preparation involving slashing, ploughing and harrowing were done with a tractor after which demarcation and marking of plots were also done, each plot measuring 3m x 3m and the plots separated by 2m path. The total area used for the trial was 71m x 13m (0.092 ha). Two cucumber seeds variety market-more were planted on the plots at a distance of 1m x 1m. There were 54 plots on the whole and the experiment was made up 18 treatments which were replicated three times arranged in a split plot design.

The treatments were

1.	G ₁	-	50%	<i>Allium sativum</i>
2.	G ₂	-	75%	<i>Allium sativum</i>
3.	G ₃	-	100%	<i>Allium sativum</i>
4.	N ₁	-	50%	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>
5.	N ₂	-	75%	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>
6.	N ₃	-	100%	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>
7.	M ₁	-	50%	<i>Moringa olifera</i>
8.	M ₂	-	75%	<i>Moringa olifera</i>
9.	M ₃	-	100%	<i>Moringa olifera</i>
10.	T ₁	-	50%	Tithonia
11.	T ₂	-	75%	Tithonia
12.	T ₃	-	100%	Tithonia
13.	O ₁	-	50%	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>
14.	O ₂	-	75%	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>
15.	O ₃	-	100%	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>
16.	WC	-	Con. water	
17.	DW	-	Distilled water	
18.	CY	-	Cypermethrine	

PREPARATION OF THE PLANT EXTRACTS

The plant materials namely *A. sativum* rhizomes, *A. indica* leaves, *Moringa olifera* leaves, tithonia leaves and *O. gratissimum* leaves used for the experiment were obtained/sourced from NIHORT premises and fields as well as from markets in Okigwe.

The plant materials apart from tithonia were allowed to dry under room temperature and in the sun for four days. The dried materials were ground to a fine powder manually with small wooden pestle and mortar and with motorized grinders. Thereafter one kilogram (1kg) each of the five ground plant materials were poured into 5-litre capacity plastic buckets. Two litres of ethanol was measured and poured into each of the five buckets containing the ground plant materials and were allowed to stay for 24 hours. The solution in the containers (five buckets) was

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sieved with muslin cloth to get the various extracts for the trial. The extracts were then allowed to stay for another 24 hours. Thereafter, they (the extracts) were sieved again with muslin cloth. The various concentrations to be used for the experiment viz 50%, 75% and 100% for each of the plant extracts were worked out; for example, for 50% concentration, 50% of the extract was mixed with 50% of water, for 75% concentration, 75% of the extract was mixed (diluted) with 25% of water while 100% of the concentration remained undiluted (was not mixed or diluted with water). The treatments (the various concentrations of the extracts) were applied on the plots of the crop with a 5-litre capacity manually operated sprayer. This commenced two weeks after crop establishment and was done at two weeks interval and for five times before the end of the trial. Also distilled water and concentrated water treatments were administered using the same application equipment and for the same duration. The cypermethrine (insecticidal check) at 12.5% E.C was also applied using the same spraying equipment and for the same period till the end of the trial.

Compound fertilizer N.P.K 20:10:10 at the rate of 200kg/ha was applied in two split doses, the first dose given two weeks after establishment while the second dose was done two weeks after flowering.

Weeding operations were done manually with hoes when necessary.

Insect collection and identification started ten days after crop emergence. These were done manually and at four days interval preferably in the early hours of the day (6.0am – 7.30am). Assessment of infestation was based on the population of the associated/identified major insect pests per plot while damage was based on the number of holes/punctures on the leaves, number of defoliated leaves and damaged fruits, due to attack by the associated insect pests.

Data collected from the trial were subjected to statistical analysis using Genstat statistical package. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) tests were conducted and means were separated using Duncan New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results show the identified major insect pests of the crop (cucumber) in 2012 and 2013 cropping seasons to include flea beetles (*Cerotoma ruficornis*), leaf-footed plant bug (*Leptoglossus australis*), cucumber beetle (*Diabrotica* spp). The population of identified insect pests was significantly ($P < 0.05$) reduced in all the tested bio-pesticides and the synthetic pesticides compared with the control in both seasons (Tables 2 and 3). Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) existed in the number of punctures on the leaves, number of defoliated leaves for all the concentrations of the bio-pesticides, synthetic pesticides (Cypermethrine) and the untreated plots. *Allium sativum*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Occimum* at 100% concentration recorded lower insect number/infestation of all the tested plant extracts in the two cropping seasons. The results also showed significant differences in the vine length, stem girth and number of leaves in all the treated plots and the control. However, cypermethrine recorded highest in all the considered growth parameters for both (2012 and 2013) cropping seasons. This was followed 100% concentration of *A. sativum*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Occimum*, *Moringa olifera* and *Tithonia* in that order. (Tables 4 and 5). At all times crops in plots sprayed with the plant extracts were less attacked than the unsprayed checks (control).

Results in Tables 6 and 7 showed the yield and damage on the cucumber fruits by the associated insect pests for the two cropping seasons (2012 and 2013). Higher yields in terms of fruit number and weight were recorded in all the tested concentrations of the bio-pesticides and the cypermethrine compared with the distilled and concentrated water which recorded lower yield and higher damage. The efficacy of cypermethrine was highest having performed best which recorded 4.78/plot and 1.12kg/plot for marketable fruit number and weight respectively in 2012 cropping season and 5.16/plot and 1.18kg/plot for fruit number and weight respectively in 2013. Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) existed between the untreated (control) and all the treated plots in insect population and yield, hence 73.4%

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reduction in insect population and 82.7% reduction in leaf damage were recorded in 2012 while that of 2013 was 81.6% and 85.3% for reduction in insect population and leaf damage respectively.

The studies showed that *Allium sativum*, *ocimum gratissimum* and *Azadirachta indica* extracts at 100% concentrations were promising among the plant materials used for the control of insect pests of cucumber in the studies in both seasons (2012 and 2013). This observation is in agreement with earlier studies by Alabi, (2009), Iwalokun *et. al*, (2003) where reduced insect infestation and increased yield on vegetable crops such as okra, water melon and cucumber were recorded by the use of these plant extracts. These plant materials as well were found to contain oleoresin oils and azadirachtin which can combat insect in various ways such as acting as anti-feedant, repellent and as insect growth inhibitor Sridhar and Vijayalakshmi, (2002) The numerous insect holes (punctures) on the leaves of cucumber was contributed by the cucumber leaf beetles during their feeding on the leaves. The population of the leaf pests decreased with the application of the plant extracts and as the plant approached maturity. This also may be related to the ageing of the leaves. (Emosairue, 2007).

CONCLUSION

The use of plant extracts especially *Allium sativum*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Ocimum* proved much better for control of insect pests of cucumber than that of *Moringa olifera* and *Tithonia*..

The results however showed that the tested plant extracts at the three different concentrations of 50%, 75% and 100% proved efficacious in the control of major cucumber insect pests and could contributed immensely to increased marketable yield .These plant materials however, are environmentally friendly as well as being available and affordable. The results of the study confirmed the insect control characteristics of the plant extracts screened.

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Table 2: Bio-pesticidal effect on insect pests of cucumber in Okigwe South-eastern Nigeria in 2012.

Treatment	Flea beetles (<i>Ceratomyza</i> <i>ruficornis</i>). Per plot.	Leaf footed plant bug(<i>Leptoglossus</i> <i>australis</i>). Per plot.	Beetles (<i>Diabrotica</i> spp) . Per plot.	Insect pest punctures on leaves.	No. of defoliated leaves.
CY	1.33 ^a	0.7 ^a	0.7 ^a	11.10 ^a	1.71 ^{ab}
DW	4.93 ⁱ	4.3 ^d	5.8 ^e	24.5 ^h	3.00 ^c
G ₁	2.92 ^{de}	2.4 ^b	2.6 ^{bc}	16.8 ^{def}	2.28 ^b
G ₂	2.75 ^d	2.0 ^b	2.3 ^b	15.4 ^{cd}	1.98 ^{ab}
G ₃	1.72 ^b	1.3 ^a	1.0 ^a	13.90 ^{be}	1.79 ^{ab}
M ₁	3.18 ^e	2.6 ^{bc}	2.8 ^c	15.73 ^d	1.70 ^{ab}
M ₂	2.97 ^{de}	2.2 ^b	2.3 ^b	13.62 ^b	1.72 ^{ab}
M ₃	2.17 ^c	1.1 ^a	1.7 ^a	13.05 ^b	1.57 ^a
N ₁	3.48 ^{gh}	3.0 ^c	3.2 ^d	18.77 ^a	2.26 ^b
N ₂	3.06 ^f	2.4 ^b	2.9 ^c	16.74 ^{def}	2.16 ^{ab}
N ₃	2.73 ^d	2.1 ^b	2.0 ^{ab}	15.68 ^d	2.02 ^{ab}
O ₁	3.35 ^{fgh}	2.8 ^{bc}	3.2 ^d	17.90 ^{efg}	2.35 ^b
O ₂	3.37 ^{fgh}	3.1 ^{bc}	2.6 ^{bc}	16.69 ^{def}	1.93 ^{ab}
O ₃	2.88 ^{de}	2.1 ^b	2.2 ^b	15.30 ^{cd}	1.87 ^{ab}
T ₁	3.60 ^h	3.1 ^{bc}	3.4 ^d	17.66 ^{efg}	1.90 ^{ab}
T ₂	3.40 ^{fgh}	3.0 ^{bc}	2.7 ^{bc}	16.23 ^{de}	2.11 ^{ab}
T ₃	2.70 ^d	2.1 ^b	2.4 ^b	16.41 ^{def}	1.86 ^{ab}
WC	4.99 ⁱ	4.4 ^d	5.8 ^e	24.00 ^h	3.50 ^c

Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$ according to Duncan New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT)

CY = Cypermethrine G = Garlic, M = *Moringa olifera*, N = Neem, O = *O. gratissimum*, T = Tithonia, WC = conc. Water, DW = Distilled water.

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Table 3: Bio-pesticidal effect on insect pests of cucumber in Okigwe South-eastern Nigeria in 2013.

Treatment	Flea beetles (<i>Cerotoma rificornis</i>). Per plot.	Leaf footed plant bug(<i>Leptoglossus australis</i>). Per plot.	Beetles (<i>Diabrotica</i> spp). Per plot.	Insect pest punctures on leaves.	No. of defoliated leaves.
CY	1.41 ^a	0.9 ^a	0.6 ^a	13.10 ^a	1.57 ^a
DW	6.21 ^a	5.2 ^d	6.3 ^e	26.50 ^h	3.20 ^c
G ₁	2.84 ^{de}	2.6 ^b	2.8 ^{bc}	16.90 ^{def}	2.35 ^b
G ₂	2.65 ^d	2.3 ^b	2.5 ^b	15.30 ^{cd}	1.86 ^{ab}
G ₃	1.84 ^b	1.5 ^a	1.3 ^a	13.93 ^{bc}	1.63 ^a
M ₁	3.20 ^e	2.8 ^{bc}	3.0 ^c	15.81 ^d	2.25 ^b
M ₂	3.00 ^{de}	2.4 ^b	2.7 ^c	16.93 ^{def}	1.76 ^{ab}
M ₃	2.13 ^c	2.1 ^b	2.0 ^{ab}	15.47 ^{ca}	2.20 ^b
N ₁	3.53 ^{gh}	2.5 ^b	3.4 ^d	16.65 ^{def}	2.18 ^{ab}
N ₂	3.27 ^f	2.0 ^b	2.1 ^{ab}	16.23 ^{de}	2.01 ^{ab}
N ₃	2.70 ^d	1.7 ^{ab}	1.7 ^a	15.35 ^{cd}	1.65 ^a
O ₁	3.39 ^{gh}	2.9 ^{bc}	2.0 ^{ab}	17.86 ^{efg}	2.16 ^{ab}
O ₂	3.35 ^{gh}	3.3 ^{bc}	2.8 ^c	16.58 ^{def}	1.91 ^{ab}
O ₃	2.86 ^{de}	2.4 ^b	2.3 ^b	15.41 ^{cd}	1.84 ^{ab}
T ₁	3.71 ^h	3.5 ^{bc}	3.3 ^d	17.73 ^{efg}	2.24 ^b
T ₂	3.48 ^{gh}	3.8 ^c	2.7 ^{bc}	16.38 ^{de}	2.36 ^b
T ₃	2.90 ^{de}	2.8 ^{bc}	2.9 ^{bc}	16.54 ^{def}	1.89 ^{ab}
WC	5.19 ⁱ	5.3 ^d	5.9 ^e	25.16 ^h	3.62 ^c

Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$ according to Duncan New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT).

CY = Cypermethrine G = Garlic, M = *Moringa olifera*, N = Neem,
O = *O. gratissimum*, T = Tithonia, WC = conc. Water, DW = Distilled water.

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Table 4: Bio-pesticidal effect on growth parameters of cucumber in Okigwe South-eastern Nigeria in 2012.

Treatment	Mean Vine Length (cm)	Mean number of leaves	Mean stem girth (cm)
CY	283.2 ^a	65.00 ^a	1.08 ^a
DW	53.7 ^d	24.00 ^d	0.55 ^b
G ₁	186.4 ^b	40.32 ^b	0.70 ^b
G ₂	160.6 ^{bc}	54.00 ^a	0.80 ^a
G ₃	256.7 ^a	58.30 ^a	0.87 ^a
M ₁	100.1 ^c	37.42 ^b	0.66 ^b
M ₂	182.6 ^b	48.70 ^{ab}	0.85 ^a
M ₃	245.3 ^a	55.40 ^a	0.90 ^a
N ₁	128.1 ^{bc}	40.21 ^b	0.70 ^{ab}
N ₂	143.2 ^{bc}	40.00 ^b	0.80 ^a
N ₃	141.8 ^{bc}	42.40 ^b	0.78 ^{ab}
O ₁	109.1 ^c	33.30 ^b	0.68 ^b
O ₂	150.4 ^{bc}	44.10 ^{ab}	0.80 ^a
O ₃	177.5 ^b	48.60 ^{ab}	0.82 ^a
T ₁	77.9 ^{cd}	32.5 ^c	0.60 ^b
T ₂	107.6 ^c	36.38 ^c	0.60 ^b
T ₃	166.3 ^{bc}	47.30 ^{ab}	0.80 ^a
WC	60.3 ^d	16.3 ^c	0.45 ^b

Means in the same column followed by different letters are significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$ according to Duncan New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT).

CY = Cypermethrine G = Garlic, M = *Moringa olifera*, N = Neem,
 O = *O. gratissimum*, T = Tithonia, WC = conc. Water, DW = Distilled water.

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Table 5: Bio-pesticidal effect on growth parameters of cucumber in Okigwe South-eastern Nigeria in 2013.

Treatment	Mean Vine Length (cm)	Mean number of leaves	Mean stem girth (cm)
CY	262.1 ^a	68.21 ^a	0.92 ^a
DW	157.3 ^{bc}	28.82 ^d	0.58 ^b
G ₁	193.0 ^{ab}	45.27 ^b	0.82 ^a
G ₂	162.4 ^{bc}	56.12 ^a	0.80 ^a
G ₃	248.6 ^a	62.00 ^a	0.95 ^a
M ₁	110.3 ^c	38.24 ^b	0.68 ^b
M ₂	184.0 ^b	47.81 ^{ab}	0.89 ^a
M ₃	198.5 ^{ab}	54.05 ^a	0.71 ^{ab}
N ₁	194.9 ^{ab}	42.12 ^b	0.83 ^a
N ₂	176.2 ^{bc}	48.66 ^{ab}	0.79 ^{ab}
N ₃	241.6 ^a	53.13 ^a	0.90 ^a
O ₁	129.7 ^c	40.22 ^b	0.69 ^b
O ₂	154.0 ^{bc}	43.21 ^{ab}	0.80 ^a
O ₃	193.6 ^b	49.82 ^{ab}	0.83 ^a
T ₁	87.9 ^{cd}	35.23 ^c	0.63 ^b
T ₂	117.3 ^c	38.63 ^c	0.81 ^a
T ₃	163.3 ^{bc}	48.12 ^{ab}	0.64 ^b
WC	62.0 ^d	27.20 ^d	0.48 ^b

Means in the same column followed by different letters are significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$ according to Duncan New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT).

CY = Cypermethrine G = Garlic, M = *Moringa olifera*, N = Neem,
O = *O. gratissimum*, T = Tithonia, WC = conc. Water, DW = Distilled water.

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Table 6: Bio-pesticidal effect on the yield of cucumber in Okigwe South-eastern Nigeria in 2012.

Treatment	Mean No. of fruits	Mean Weight of fruits (kg)	Mean No of damaged fruit per plot	Mean weight of damaged fruits per plot (kg)
CY	4.78 ^a	1.12 ^a	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a
DW	1.39 ^{bed}	0.30 ^d	2.3 ^c	0.35 ^{bc}
G ₁	1.75 ^{bcd}	0.32 ^{db}	0.2 ^{bc}	0.15 ^b
G ₂	1.96 ^{bcd}	0.39 ^d	0.2 ^{bc}	0.14 ^b
G ₃	3.53 ^{ab}	0.84 ^{abc}	0.00 ^a	0.00 ^a
M ₁	2.08 ^{bcd}	0.44 ^{cd}	0.22 ^{bc}	0.21 ^b
M ₂	1.6 ^{cd}	0.37 ^d	0.4 ^b	0.10 ^b
M ₃	3.47 ^{abc}	0.90 ^{ab}	0.0 ^b	0.0 ^a
N ₁	3.00 ^{bcd}	0.33 ^d	0.4 ^b	0.10 ^b
N ₂	1.53 ^d	0.36 ^d	0.32 ^b	0.20 ^b
N ₃	2.83 ^{bcd}	0.60 ^{bcd}	0.1 ^b	0.13 ^b
O ₁	1.48 ^d	0.34 ^d	0.48 ^b	0.153 ^b
O ₂	2.52 ^{bcd}	0.52 ^{bcd}	0.4 ^{bc}	0.15 ^b
O ₃	2.61 ^{bcd}	0.61 ^{bcd}	0.4 ^b	0.10 ^b
T ₁	1.78 ^{bcd}	0.41 ^d	1.2 ^c	0.21 ^b
T ₂	2.28 ^{bcd}	0.53 ^{bcd}	0.8 ^b	0.21 ^b
T ₃	2.00 ^{bcd}	0.37 ^d	0.4 ^b	0.12 ^b
WC	1.39 ^d	0.27 ^d	2.1 ^c	0.30 ^{bc}

Means followed by the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$ according to Duncan New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT).

CY = Cypermethrine G = Garlic, M = *Moringa olifera*, N = Neem,
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Table 7: Bio-pesticidal effect on the yield of cucumber in Okigwe South-eastern Nigeria in 2013.

Treatment	Mean No. of fruits	Mean Weight of fruits (kg)	Mean No of damaged fruit per plot	Mean weight of damaged fruits per plot (kg)
CY	5.16 ^a	1.18 ^a	0.09 ^a	0.01 ^a
DW	1.36 ^{bcd}	0.27 ^d	2.60 ^c	0.37 ^{bc}
G ₁	1.73 ^{bcd}	0.35 ^d	0.21 ^{bc}	0.18 ^b
G ₂	2.01 ^{bcd}	0.43 ^d	0.23 ^{bc}	0.16 ^b
G ₃	3.62 ^{ab}	1.05 ^{ab}	0.09 ^a	0.01 ^a
M ₁	1.97 ^{bcd}	0.40 ^{cd}	0.26 ^{bc}	0.19 ^b
M ₂	1.81 ^{cd}	0.33 ^d	0.14 ^{ab}	0.16 ^b
M ₃	2.23 ^{bcd}	0.51 ^{bcd}	0.22 ^{bc}	0.18 ^b
N ₁	3.10 ^{bcd}	0.37 ^d	0.16 ^{ab}	0.11 ^b
N ₂	1.67 ^{cd}	0.45 ^{cd}	0.36 ^b	0.23 ^b
N ₃	3.00 ^{bcd}	0.73 ^{ab}	0.08 ^a	0.01 ^a
O ₁	1.51 ^{cd}	0.39 ^d	0.39 ^b	0.24 ^b
O ₂	1.76 ^{bcd}	0.41 ^d	0.43 ^b	0.29 ^b
O ₃	2.86 ^{bcd}	0.56 ^{cd}	0.40 ^b	0.22 ^b
T ₁	1.81 ^{bcd}	0.43 ^d	1.25 ^c	0.31 ^{bc}
T ₂	2.31 ^{bcd}	0.52 ^{bcd}	0.86 ^b	0.27 ^b
T ₃	1.98 ^{bcd}	0.33 ^d	0.43 ^b	0.18 ^b
WC	1.41	0.29 ^d	2.30 ^c	0.33 ^{bc}

Means followed by the same letter in the same column are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$ according to Duncan New Multiple Range Test (DNMRT).

CY = Cypermethrine G = Garlic, M = *Moringa olifera*, N = Neem,
O = *O. gratissimum*, T = Tithonia, WC = conc. Water, DW = Distilled water.

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